

The Research Process

- Literature Review.
- NS Heritage Directory.
- NS Heritage Web Presence.
- Int'l Heritage Portals.
- Informal Information Gathering.
- Electronic Questionnaire.

Project Mission

Create a single access point for the Nova Scotia Heritage Community.

Unify the Heritage Community.

Provide access to professional practise information.

Our Findings

- Desire for a unified marketing resource.
- Desire for a single heritage list serv.
- Desire for ready access to experts.
- Desire for access to professional practise information.
- Support for Portal content contribution.
- Support for reciprocal linking.

Plan Recommendations

- Action 1 - Improved Communications.
- Action 2 - Increase Heritage Profile.
- Action 3 - Enhance the Heritage Directory.
- Action 4 - Determine Leadership.
- Action 5 - Resource Web Site.
- Action 6 - Portal Design.

Heritage Portal Plan Final Report

<http://www.library.dal.ca/duasc/research>

Teshekkür Ederim

Thank You